

Zenodo Deposit — File Manifest (README)

Ilya V. Osipov · 2026 · DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20688771 · **Version 8**

Deposit: Diacritic Reduction and Restoration in Serbo-Croatian (*šišana / dešišavanje*): Research Data and Methods. **Author:** Ilya V. Osipov (ORCID 0000-0002-8017-8153). **License:** CC BY 4.0 (documents); bundled dictionaries carry their own source licenses (see NOTICE / DATA-LICENSE). **Pinned source:** ioDiacritics commit [confirm current commit after coverage expansion], main.

What changed in version 8. This version replaces the preprint with **Preprint 2 — "One Language for Diacritics: Operational Equivalence of Bosnian, Croatian and Serbian in Diacritic Restoration"**, in English and in a neutral Serbo-Croatian (BHS) register. Preprint 2 adds an independent Universal Dependencies benchmark against the corpus-trained tool REDI, an efficiency/deployability analysis (a ~12.82 MB on-device restorer vs multi-gigabyte context models), a claims-and-evidence-status table, and **updated lexical statistics on coverage-expanded lexicons** (union 250,862; standard-independence 99.51%). See the Notes on number consistency below.

Files in this deposit

Preprint (the main text) — UPDATED in v8

1. **Preprint2_One_Language_for_Diacritics_EN_v8.pdf** — Preprint 2, English (public deposit version, 18 pp.). The primary scholarly text: the operational-equivalence thesis (>99.5%), the structural mechanism (divergence on the form axis, not the diacritic axis), the unification result, contamination and norm-detection analyses, an independent UD benchmark vs REDI, an efficiency/deployability section, a claims-and-evidence-status table, and data appendices (aggregate counts + representative samples; full lists reproducible from open data and available on request).
2. **Preprint2_Jedan_jezik_za_dijakritiku_BHS_v8.pdf** — Preprint 2, neutral Serbo-Croatian / BHS register (ijekavica, Latin script, internationalism-based; 9 pp.). Full article translation; its data appendices point to the English file 1 and the data package.

Research-data companion — carried forward from v7 (to be regenerated for the new numbers — see Notes)

3. **diacritic_restoration_research_data.pdf** — Companion (English): phenomenon and framing, algorithm, data and dictionary construction, the two studies, the symmetric experiment, reproducibility, provenance, related work.
4. **diacritic_restoration_research_data.md** — Markdown source of file 3 (editable archival).
5. **diacritic_restoration_research_data_sh.pdf** — Serbo-Croatian companion (neutral register), section-for-section equivalent of file 3.
6. **diacritic_restoration_research_data_sh.md** — Markdown source of file 5.

Supplementary data — carried forward from v7

7. **data Tier 1 — Diacritic Restoration.pdf** — resolution tables (schema, statistics, representative rows), task inventory (C1/C2/C3 classes, ceiling, minimal pairs), aggregate results table, and the reverse-index dictionaries with provenance and licenses.
8. **data Tier 2 — Diacritic Restoration.pdf** — figure data and captions, per-pack reliability passports, code-switching collision inventories, sociolinguistic measurements, and evaluation-cell provenance and licenses.

This document — UPDATED in v8

9. **Zenodo_deposit_file_manifest_v8.pdf** — This manifest.

Machine-readable data (available from the pinned repository)

`results_aggregate.tsv`, `ambiguous_resolution_set.tsv`, `final_inventory.json`, the reverse-index dictionaries (after coverage expansion: per-standard 170,365 / 162,686 / 116,777 keys; 250,862-key union), the evaluation/build tool set, and the pre-experiment reports. Repository and demos: URLs as pinned in the source commit (see previous manifest). (*Raw bald→accented dictionaries are not redistributed in the preprint; the preprint provides aggregate counts, representative samples, the reproduction pipeline and checksums, and full lists are reproducible from the open frequency lists / available on request.*)

Notes on number consistency (v8)

- The **Preprint 2 files (1-2) are authoritative for the current numbers**: they reflect the coverage-expanded lexicons (union 250,862; genuinely-competing diacritization 0.49%; standard-independence 99.51%; Serbian benchmark recall 93.4%).
- The **carried-forward companion and supplementary files (3-8) reflect the earlier (pre-expansion) lexicons** (union 240,384; 99.57%). They are scheduled to be regenerated to match Preprint 2; until then, where numbers differ, the Preprint 2 files take precedence. (*Decision pending: regenerate 3-8 for this version, or keep as-is with this note.*)

How to cite

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